

Regional Planning in Rajasthan: A Micro Level Study of Deoli Tehsil

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Abstract

The present study is an attempt to analyse the socio economic development of Deoli Tehsil of Tonk district of Rajasthan. An in-depth study and detailed analysis of existing pattern of physical, cultural environment and local rural resources has been undertaken to seek a balanced and speedy development for the Deoli Tehsil through optimum utilization of available resources. Attainment of aforesaid purpose is attempted by identification of existing urban hierarchy, network linkages, service centres and by proposing new ones which can fill in the functional gaps and have the potential of becoming the nuclei for future development.

Keywords: Centrality, Hierarchy, Weightage, service center

Today every nation of the world, whatever its political social and economic system, favours a policy of balanced economic, social political and regional development. Planning and development as it exists today at micro level in the Indian context, does not seem to have any specific or special consideration, it operates within the mainstream of national and state planning principles, without a proper analysis of the problems, prospects, potentialities and requirements of the people and the economy concern of the sub region. The present study is an effort to find out effective solution of different problems under micro level planning plan.

Objectives of the study

The present research work aims to seek the balanced development of the relatively smaller area such as the Deoli tehsil. This aim can be achieved by sound micro regional planning of the Deoli tehsil by using following objectives;

- To test the value for each central function.
- Present study attempts to find the existing transport linkage in different production and market centres.
- To find out the existing potential of economic opportunities and to provide encouragement to possible industries which depend directly or indirectly on agriculture so that avenues for employment may be opened in the tehsil.
- To find the gaps and problems in sectoral and spatial regions.

Methodology

In the present study different methods have been employed from sister disciplines such as economics, statistics and other sciences. It is based on field survey. The information was later analysed by various quantitative methods.

The Study Area

Deoli tehsil predominantly lies in the Southern portion of Tonk district. The study area extends from 25° 44'N to 25° 58' N Latitudes and from 75° 10' E to 75° 52' E Longitudes. It is bounded in the North by Todaraisingh tehsil in the East by Hindoli tehsil and in the West by Kekri tehsil and Jahazpur tehsils in the South.

Deoli tehsil has a total area of 1228.35 sq.km. with a population of 214408 persons. The tehsil

has its headquarters at Deoli. There are 186 villages and one urban centre in the tehsil. Out of the 186 villages only 169 are inhabited.

The Concept of Central Functions

Central functions are those which by their nature are available in a few settlements but are availed of by a number of settlements. The central place theory, therefore, has classified central functions as higher and lower order functions. According to detailed observation of the study area, we have considered here those functions which have influenced the social and economic status of people such as education, medical, postal, marketing, banking and other aspects of their day to day life have been chosen as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Population size of settlements with their functional distribution

Pop. Size	No. of Settl.	Pr.Sc	Upp Pri Sch.	High Sch.	H.Se Sch.	Health Cent	Disp.	Hosp .	Ferti.	Rati on	Bank	Who Mar k	Vete.	Bus serv.
0-199	16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
200-499	45	24	2	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	2
500-1999	88	90	38	16	2	-	-	-	19	46	-	-	1	38
2000-4999	13	18	14	12	6	2	5	-	12	13	7	13	2	9
5000-above	8	33	17	11	9	5	8	3	8	8	8	8	7	8
Total	170	141	69	39	17	7	13	3	40	68	15	21	10	58

Clustering of Central Functions and Sub-Functions

Clustering of functions is directly influenced by the population of the centres. Therefore, the settlements have been categorized according to their population size in the table 2.

Total number of functions considered here are

1.Education, 2.Medical, 3.Drinking water, 4.Electricity, 5.Public Distribution System
6.RestHouses,7.Banking,8.Entertainment,9.Telecommunications,10.Cooperatives, 11.Administrative,12. Fertilizer,13. Veterinary, 14. Transportations and 15.Market.

Size of Settlements (Population)	Total No. of Settlements	Total No. of functions available in individual settlements															
		Nil	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
0-199	16	1	14	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
200-499	45	-	2	21	19	2	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
500-1999	88	-	-	-	-	8	21	22	10	6	6	8	5	2	-	-	-
2000-4999	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	2	4	2	2	-
5000-above	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	4
Total	170	1	16	22	19	10	21	22	12	6	7	9	7	6	2	6	4

The following observation can be made here

(a) Higher functions and sub-functions like education up to higher secondary, hospitals, post office, banks, veterinary hospitals, entertainment institutions and police facility are found in those settlements with population above 2000 persons. It is a remarkable point to note that there is a wide gap in the distribution of functions on the basis of population size of settlements. There are few settlements with population 500-1999 having any of the above facilities.

(b) Settlements below 500 populations are lacking in the functions and services. Some of these settlements are decorated with a telegraph, electricity, bus services.

(c) Settlements between 500-1999 population sizes are decorated further with education, primary health sub center, internet café, bus services, veterinary services, drinking water, electricity public distribution system and panchayat centres.

Functional Hierarchy

The term settlement hierarchy denotes a ranking of settlements into successive groups on the basis of their population or functions. In the present study central places, hierarchy and their classification have been determined on the basis of central functions. In this exercise the weights to different sub-functions are assigned according to their distribution among all the settlements, on the basis of the principle, the fewer the settlements having a particular function the greater importance in terms of centrality and therefore higher the weightage. The weightage of functions/sub functions has been determined on the basis of Bhat's formula i.e. $W_i = \frac{N}{F_i}$ Where

W_i = Weightage to the i th sub-function.

F_i = Number of settlements having the function/sub function

N = Total number of settlements.

Table 3.
Weight scores for the Variables

S.No	Functions & sub functions	No. of settlements where they occur	Weightage
1.	Educational		
	i) Primary school	108	1.5
	ii) Middle school	56	3.03

	iii) High school	36	4.7
	iv) Higher secondary school	14	12.1
	v) College	3	56.6
2.	Medical		
	i) Health centers	7	24.2
	ii) Primary Health center	11	15.4
	iii) Medical dispensary	13	13.07
	iv) Medical hospitals	3	56.6
3.	Veterinary hospitals	9	18.8
4.	Public utility services		
	i) Drinking water	35	4.8
	ii) Electricity	163	1.04
	iii.) Ration shops	68	2.5
	iv) Lodging facility	7	24.2
5.	Banking	15	11.3
6.	Entertainment		
	i.) Dish antennas	52	3.2
	ii) Cinema houses	9	18.8
	iii) Library	8	21.2
7.	Fertilizer and seed shop	40	4.2
8.	Administration		
	(a) Tehsil headquarter	1	170
	(b) Panchayat headquarter	39	4.3
9.	Markets		
	i) Retail markets	154	1.1
	ii) Wholesale markets	21	8.09
10.	Transportations	58	2.9
11.	Communications		
	i) Post offices	5	34
	ii) Couriers	5	34

Determination of Centrality

The centrality of settlements has been calculated with the help of the following formula.

$$C_j = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i X_{ij}$$

Where, C_j = Composite value for that function for j th settlement.

k = total number of sub functions under a given function.

W_i = Weightage to the i th sub function.

X_{ij} = Value of i th sub function in j th settlement

Hierarchical Order

After having calculated the centrality of all the settlements, they are plotted on a double log graph because as the settlements vary in population size from 16 (Narsinghpura) to 22065 (Deoli town) and centrality vary from 1.0 (Thali etc.) to 1050.72 (Deoli town).

Functional Centrality and Population Size

The centrality score and population size have a positive high correlation ($r = 0.94$) in the study area which has been worked out with the help of Karl Pearson's method. The area under study has 170 inhabited settlements including one urban settlement. These settlements have been categorized into five groups on the basis of functional gaps of double log graph. The following table shows the number of settlements with their levels according to their centrality score.

Table 4.
Number of settlement according to Hierarchical Order

Hierarchical level	Centrality score	No.of settlements	Percent of total
I	More than 500	2	1.18
II	200-500	7	4.11
III	50-200	14	8.23
IV	25-50	22	12.94
V	Less than 25	125	73.54
Total		170	100.00

It is evident from table 4 that with the increase in the order of hierarchy, the number of settlements shows decline in number. The maximum number of settlements comes in the fifth category, which includes 125 settlements. Most of these settlements have either of any one or two functions. The fourth category is formed by large villages, which by virtue of central location in their respective regions have become important service centres. The third category of hierarchy includes only 14 settlements. The second hierarchical level includes seven settlements. The first category of hierarchy includes only two

settlements i.e., Deoli town and Dooni with 1050.72 and 543.46 centrality scores respectively.

Final ranking and Hierarchy of Settlements on the basis of Composite Indices

The final hierarchy of settlements has been determined on the basis of composite centrality of the settlements of the Deoli tehsil. The composite centrality is calculated by adding the centrality values of functions and occupation.

This study reveals that the hierarchy of settlements on above basis has lead to confusing

conclusions. Small size settlements, based on population hierarchy do not give the correct level. It is because most of the non-primary workers, employed in a large central place, come daily from the near by villages. So hierarchy based on population is not so much helpful in making the plan for regional development. The hierarchy of settlements based on functions obtained from direct sources gives a right level of hierarchy and the results derived from this functional data are therefore useful for the regional planning and development.

Areas of Functional Deficiency

For simplification of study the functions have been divided into 3 groups according to accessibility the higher services (radius 8km), medium services (radius 5km) and lower services (radius 3km).

Deficiency areas of higher Services

The study reveals that only the areas around major centres are of functional adequacy while other parts of the tehsil form the deficiency areas. This is due to concentration of major services at regional centres viz. Deoli town and Dooni. All these centres are situated along the metalled road.

Deficiency Areas of Medium Services

It is clear from the study that deficient areas are more in comparison to the areas of adequate services in Deoli tehsil. It means that the spatial distribution of such services is highly unbalanced which has revealed the maximum deficient areas.

Proposals for Spatio Functional Planning

Functional hierarchy of service centres in the tehsil consists of five orders (Map1). After a careful examination of functions, we find that few of the areas are highly developed whereas others are less developed. It has been decided that the service centres should be distributed according to the various orders, their serving capacity and served area. The table 5. shows the average spacing, proposed, existing and required number of service centres according to their hierarchical order. The Deoli tehsil will have 56 proposed service centres to fill up the areas of functional gaps, on the basis of above considerations. Out of these 14 centres are existing centres. So 42 new centres will be required (Map2).

map-1

Table 5
Proposed, Existing and Required Number of Service centres

Hierarchical Order	Centres	Proposed Centres	Existing Centres
I	Regional capital	1	1
II	Reg. service centres	3	2
III	Service centres	12	8
IV	Central villages	40	3
V	Dependent villages	114	156

Conclusion

The existence of settlement hierarchy and distribution of service centres in any region depends to a large extent upon physical, economic and cultural factors. We find that in the region under study, physical and socio-economic constraints have suppressed economic

development. The region is backward in all respects. Agriculture, being the main occupation and base of economy, needs special plans for development in terms of more land for cultivation and increase in inputs like hybrid seeds, fertilisers, irrigation and mechanization.

Agro based industries can form the basis of

industrial development. Special attention needs to be paid to provision of better social and infrastructure services like education, health, drinking water, electricity and entertainment. All this would be possible only when transport network is enhanced and improved. To conclude all the above steps would be fruitful and optimum results of balanced development of a micro region like Deoli would be attained only by a planned and balanced distribution of rural and urban settlements and provision of adequate organisational facilities.

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